

ISic3645

I.Sicily inscription 3645

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula ansata

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

'sulle falde del Calvario, in contrada Panneria, dove esistono ruderi di antiche fabbriche', found during stone quarrying

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 22225

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. Notizie degli scavi di antichità. At 411

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